

**QUELQUES PRINCIPES DE FONCTIONNEMENT
DES BASES TERMINOLOGIQUES ET DES MÉMOIRES DE TRADUCTION /
SOME OPERATING PRINCIPLES OF TERMINOLOGY BASES
AND TRANSLATION MEMORIES**

Ioana-Crina PRODAN, Associate Professor, PhD
(“Stefan cel Mare” University of Suceava, Romania)

crina.prodan@usm.ro, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1587-5470>

Received: June 1, 2025 | Reviewed: June 3, 2025 | Accepted: June 5, 2025

UDC 81 | DOI from Zenodo

Our research aims to explain some of the operating principles of certain essential tools for translators: terminology databases and translation memories. While terminology databases provide valuable support for ensuring the consistency and accuracy of translations, translation memories are more focused on reducing translation costs and better managing the time allocated to the translation process. We will highlight the role of these two tools in accelerating and standardizing the translator’s work, while integrating other tools involved in computer-assisted translation. Automation and structured storage of linguistic data can help organize and systematize information content in a more technical manner to enable faster information sharing.